

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

OBTAINING, RESEARCH AND APPLICATION OF ION EXCHANGER RESINS BASED ON COOLIGOMERS

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Abstract

At present, the chemistry of high-molecular compounds is one of the fastest growing areas of independent science. In modern times, there is not a single area of human activity in which high-molecular compounds are not used.

High-molecular compounds have existed since very ancient times. However, many believe that these compounds became known by chemists after obtaining them artificially or synthetically. This is not the right idea. Thus, while the synthetic production of member substances began at the beginning of the XIX century, high-molecular compounds were known even before 100 thousand years. Since its inception, humans have always been in contact with high-molecular compounds in their daily lives. So, cellulose wool fibers, which are the basis of wood, skin wheat starch, which is the basis of potatoes, etc. it is included in the order of highmolecular compounds. They feed people, dress them, provide them with medicines, etc. it is necessary. For this, the science of chemistry, including the preparation of compositional materials on the basis of chemical compounds, new and used for various purposes, is one of the pressing problems of the day. All this has always been the most important funds for life.

One of the important directions of modern chemistry is the obtaining of materials with new composition and necessary properties that can replace natural existing materials and their application in various fields of Industry [1].

The application of high-molecular ion-exchange compounds in various fields of Science and technology is one such direction. The research work carried out also relates to this topic.

Ion-exchange resin high-molecular compounds are produced in various types in the UK, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Japan and other countries.

Currently, the industry produces ionites (ion exchanger resins) of the following general grouping:

КУ — cationite "универсальный", strong acid cationite;

КБ — cationite "буферный", weak acid cationite;

АВ — anionite "высокоосновный", strong essential anionite;

АН — anionitis "низкоосновный", weak essential anionitis.

Most ion exchanger resins made on the basis of high-molecular compounds are solid, insoluble, compounds with limited swelling capacity [2-3].

Ion-modifiers based on cooligomers modified with nitrogen-containing compounds were used for various purposes and positive results were obtained [4-5].

Ion exchanger resins are those that contain many functional groups in their composition, including -OH, >NH, -NH₂, -COOH, etc. as they belong to polyfunctional compounds, their application areas are different.

Sulfocationite prepared on the basis of modified cooligomer was used in softening of technical water and positive results were obtained.

In laboratory conditions, tests were carried out to reduce the water hardness by trilometric method and positive results were obtained.

Sulfocationites based on functionalized cooligomers are recommended to be used in softening of technical water in thermal power plants.

The innovation in the research work is to synthesize an environmentally friendly and economically viable ion exchanger resin with a new composition and explore its application areas.

Keywords: modification, copolycondensation, oligomer, sulfocationite, ion-modifier.

Experimental part. In the research work, the resorcine-formaldehyde oligomer was first modified with urea, and then sulfocationite was obtained.

Soligomer-based sulfocationites (ion exchangers) outperform aluminosilicates and sulfolated coal in their active ion-exchange resin capacity and chemical durability.

In a flask with a volume of 250 ml, 40 g of cooligomer and 120 g of 96% solid sulfuric acid are placed and heated to about 140^oc. After the cooligomer is completely dissolved, the solution (mixture) is cooled to room temperature, and then poured into a porcelain bowl, immediately adding 30 ml of 37% formalin. The porcelain is then fixed in the bowl for 2 hours. After

cooling, it is washed off with water (until a neutral reaction). The obtained sulfocationate decomposes into particles 1-3 mm in size.

For comparison, the modified resorcine-formaldehyde oligomer was sulfoized under the same conditions and applied in parallel in its main indicators (Table1).

Table1

The main indicators of ion exchangers based on modified and unmodified resorcine-formaldehyde oligomers

№	Ion exchangers	Functional groups	Particle size, mm	Pour volume g/ml	Degree of inflatability %	Actual density kg/m ³	Specific volume ml/g
1.	Sulfocationite based on unmodified resorcine-formaldehyde oligomer	-SO ₃ -OH	1-3	0,605	0,18	1256,2	0,9
2.	Modified resorcine-formaldehyde oligomer based sulfocationite	-SO ₃ -OH -NH -CO	1-3	0,833	0,33	1672,7	1,5

The IR-spectra of the unmodified resorcine-formaldehyde oligomer and the modified resorcine-formaldehyde cooligomer have been studied. (Figure 1and 2).

Photo 1. IR-spectrum of unmodified resorsine-formaldehyde cooligomer

Photo 2. IR-spectrum of modified resorsine-formaldehyde cooligomer

It was found that valence vibrations characteristic of carbonyl ($-CO$) and amine ($>NH$) groups in modified resorcine-formaldehyde oligomer and unmodified cooligomer in IR-spectra corresponding to absorption bands in the range of $600-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed in $1644.85-1719.39\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and deformation vibrations were observed in 1041.32 cm^{-1} bands. Also observed in

IR-spectra valence and deformation vibration $C=C$ group $1644.85 - 3392.29\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (deformation); $-CH$ group 727.45 cm^{-1} (valence); $-OH$ group $1644.85-1651.88\text{ cm}^{-1}$ absorption bands are reflected.

Also, the IR-spectrum was studied in ion exchanger resins based on the non-modified and modified resorcine-formaldehyde cooligomer (Figures 3 and 4).

Photo 3. IR-spectrum of ion-modifier based on unmodified resorcine-formaldehyde cooligomer

Photo 4. IR-spectrum of ion exchanger resin based on modified resorcine-formaldehyde cooligomer

The observation of SO_3 groups in absorption bands $1644.85-1544.88\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in IR spectrum in sulfocationites based on unmodified resorcine-formaldehyde oligomer and modified resorcine-formaldehyde cooligomers shows that the obtaining of sulfocationite by interaction of solid sulfuric acid with oligomer and cooligomers occurs due to chemical bonds. It is assumed that methylol groups easily bond with sulfuric

acid, resulting in the entry into the benzene ring $-SO_3$ groups.

DTA and TGA analyzes were also carried out to determine the temperature indicators of ion exchanger resins (Figures 5 and 6). Thermogravimetric study of samples was carried out on the Netzsch Sta 449F3STA449F3A-0836-M apparatus, in the temperature range of $20-9000\text{C}$, in an inert medium.

Photo 5. DTA and TGA analyses of unmodified resorcinine-formaldehyde cooligomer based ion exchange resin

Photo 6. DTA and TGA analysis of modified resorcin-formaldehyde cooligomer based ion exchange resin

From the DTA and TGA curves, it was found that the destruction process of sulfocationite goes through three stages. Residual mass loss was 5.29% in unmodified resorcinine-formaldehyde cooligomer-based ion exchange and 2.85% in unmodified resorcinine-formaldehyde cooligomer-based ion change.

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